

2nd TwiNSol-CECs Workshop

Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants Mitigation
with Cutting-Edge Technologies

Book of Abstracts

University of Novi Sad
Faculty of Technology Novi Sad
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2nd TwiNSol-CECs Workshop
*Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants
Mitigation with Cutting-Edge Technologies*

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University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad,
Novi Sad, Serbia, 6-7 June 2024

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Mitigation with Cutting-Edge Technologies**

**University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad (TFNS), Novi Sad, Serbia,
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EFFECT OF SODIUM CHLORIDE ON THE REMOVAL OF PHARMACEUTICALLY ACTIVE COMPOUNDS FROM WATER BY A REVERSE OSMOSIS MEMBRANE

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Pharmaceutically active compounds are often detected in the aquatic environment, including surface waters, ground waters and even drinking water, due to their insufficient removal by conventional wastewater treatments. Due to adverse effects of pharmaceutically active compounds on human health and the environment, additional methods for their removal from water sources are required. Membrane separation processes, including reverse osmosis, are considered to be one of the possible solutions for the removal of the corresponding contaminants from the aquatic environment. The aim of this study was to determine the efficiency of commercially available polyamide reverse osmosis membrane (SW30HR, FilmTec™) in the removal of four pharmaceutically active compounds (acetaminophen, carbamazepine, salbutamol and bezafibrate) from model water solution and evaluate the impact of sodium chloride addition on the removal of selected compounds. Experiments were conducted in METCell® dead-end unit from EVONIK (Germany) and the pressure of 30 bar set using a nitrogen gas cylinder. Rejections (%) from 86.28% to 96.53% were achieved with SW30HR membrane for all selected compounds without the addition of sodium chloride to the feed solution. However, addition of sodium chloride in the feed solution negatively impacted the removal of selected compounds, with the rejections from 64.35% to 80.58%. The highest impact of sodium chloride was observed for bezafibrate and salbutamol, with a total decrease in rejection of 23.13% and 21.94%, respectively. Addition of sodium chloride affected the diffusion of the selected compounds through the membrane by increasing the osmotic pressure and therefore, decreasing the removal of selected compounds.

Keywords: Reverse osmosis, Water treatment, Sodium chloride, Membrane separation processes

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